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about 205 words

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The Deepest

by John Leo Lopez Pilit

The universe is decaying, and the spaceship needs John.

Only a few remnants of billions of stars can now be seen wandering in the night sky, lighting the very old Earth. The moon has already been mined. The sun has consumed all of its energy, and almost half of the biggest stars have fallen into the deepest space.

The universe is decaying so rapidly that light has even lost its ability to travel to the farthest reaches. The old Earth, after thriving for 25 billion years, should now be abandoned.

The last hope of humankind, the largest spaceship, Novaprion, is about to leave the planet tomorrow at six in the morning.

Decisions have already been made: go as deep as possible, hoping to arrive beyond the unimaginable. Whatever is waiting in the unexplored part of the dying universe—be it an untouched cluster of galaxies or even a new cosmos—does not matter at all.

“Commander, we have detected an enormous, strange object heading toward Earth, still unidentified.”

Nothing but destroyed planets and a bombarded moon can be seen in the sky, with no signs of any threat. But suddenly, the surroundings turned dull. There was a problem with time.

Novaprión must leave, but where is John?

THE END